

THE DISCREPANCY OF FORM AND CONTENT OF THE VOICE CATEGORY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the differences in form and meaning of the voice category in two languages. It examines how the voice categories (passive and active) in English and Uzbek are grammatically represented and highlights the inconsistencies between their logical and semantic meanings. Through analytical and comparative linguistic methods, the article reveals unique characteristics of voice in each language and demonstrates the challenges this creates in the teaching process.*

Keywords: *voice category, passive form, active form, grammatical inconsistency, linguistic analysis, comparative linguistics, form and content, language teaching challenges.*

In English, certain instances in the construction of active and passive voices reveal discrepancies between form and content. Fundamentally, "form" and "content" are philosophical concepts that are applicable across various scientific fields. Content represents a combination of essential elements and changes that define an object, while form expresses the existence, internal, and external structure of that content. As stated, "Just as a specific content is always expressed in a specific form, a specific form always has a specific content. Every object in existence exists due to the unity of its form and content. Content, by its essence, is primary over form"[1]. When form and content do not align, a new form arises that matches the content. The dialectic of form and content varies across scientific fields and is explained differently. In linguistics, specific content is inherently manifested in a specific form, which applies to the category of voice and its meanings. In both Uzbek and English, a sentence may be in one form of voice while conveying a different meaning. In such cases, translators face the challenge of balancing form and content, and they must prioritize content to resolve the issue correctly, as essence should always be primary.

Here, the great poet Alisher Navoi's insightful lines illustrate the importance of content:

"In poetry, true value lies in meaning;

Regardless of its appearance, meaning is key.

A poem without value in meaning

Fails to captivate the insightful mind".

This concept is relevant in English, where the pronoun "they" can imply a passive meaning in certain sentences, despite being in active form[2]. For example:

They will be cleaning the roads this time tomorrow.

This sentence could be translated into Uzbek as:

Ertaga shu payt yo'llar tozalanayotgan bo'ladi. or *Ertaga shu payt yo'llarni tozalayotgan bo'lishadi.*

In both cases, the meaning remains unchanged, but the voice differs. The first sentence is formed in the passive voice, while the second uses a cooperative voice. It becomes evident that the English pronoun "they" is not translated into Uzbek, as it merely implies the responsible parties (in this case, the authorities). Indicating the doer in this context is unnecessary. While the meaning is passive, the sentence cannot be structured in the passive voice in English, as there is no passive

form for this tense. For instance, *The roads will be being cleaned this time tomorrow* would be grammatically incorrect. Thus, although the passive meaning is expressed through "they," the sentence is constructed in the active voice, necessitating certain modifications in translation. The sentence is either translated in the passive voice or as an indefinite-person sentence, which, while conveying the idea of an agent, cannot specify the doer within the sentence structure. In other words, the indefinite-person sentence is similar in function to sentences structured in the passive voice.

Overall, this form-content discrepancy is also present in the application of the voice category in English, manifesting in certain transformations during the translation of such sentences.

According to researchers, the adequacy of a translation is determined by its full compatibility with the original text and the equivalent effect it produces on the listener (or reader). Thus, the completeness (adequacy) of a translation depends not only on the correct choice of linguistic tools but also on the appropriate use of non-linguistic elements. Factors such as who created the text, for what purpose, in which style, and under what circumstances it is used, are also significant in the translation process. The passive voice in English is one of the grammatical structures that can be challenging to translate into other languages. In sentences with a verb in the passive voice, the subject represents the person or thing receiving the action, rather than the one performing it. It should be noted that verbs in the passive voice are used more frequently in English compared to other languages. This can be explained by the fact that "in English, the passive voice is the only tool available for constructing a sentence without specifying the doer, most nouns lack case markers, and passive verbs can take various types of complements".

In fact, in English, verbs in the active voice function as predicates in most sentences, forming the bulk of the text. Most English passive voice verbs are not translated into other languages using the passive voice[3]. For example, in her research on the translation of literary texts, N.T. Satullayeva notes that only a quarter of English passive voice verbs are translated into Karakalpak - a language related to Uzbek - using the passive voice. In most cases, English passive verbs are derived from active verbs. When verbs in the active voice are converted to the passive voice, the roles of the agent and the object in the sentence are reversed. In other words, as a result of this transformation, the agent (performer of the action) moves into the position of the object in the passive voice. The changes in verbs, agents, and objects when transitioning from active to passive voice are illustrated in the following schema:

ACTIVE VOICE: AGENT – VERB – OBJECT

PASSIVE VOICE: OBJECT – BE + VERB – BY + AGENT

The transformations that occur when active verbs in English sentences shift to the passive voice are further exemplified below:

Nargiza sold the car; and *The car was sold by Nargiza.*

It becomes clear that verbs in the active voice dominate English texts and form the majority of the verbs used in sentences. Verbs used in the active voice can also be converted to the passive voice. In English, verbs in the passive voice are formed with the auxiliary verb *be* and the main verb in its Past Participle form, as illustrated in the following formula:

Be + Past Participle.

When a sentence with a verb in the passive voice is in a particular tense, the verb *be* takes the corresponding tense, which inevitably influences its translation. For instance, the following

sentence in the Present Perfect Tense in the active voice changes to the passive voice as shown below:

I have just opened the door (active voice);

The door has just been opened (passive voice).

These sentences can be translated into Uzbek as follows:

Men hozirgina eshikni ochdim; and Eshik hozirgina ochildi.

In Uzbek sentences, we can observe that the tense forms express the past. The object in the first sentence becomes the subject in the second, and the transitive verb becomes intransitive. These are normative cases in the transformation from active to passive voice. This translation of the passive voice is an example of adequate (complete) translation.

As noted, the passive voice can only be formed with prepositional phrases in the Future Continuous, Present Perfect Continuous, Past Perfect Continuous, and Future Continuous tenses. When forming the passive voice in this way, the noun form of the verb used in the active voice is employed, with the necessary preposition preceding that noun, as shown below:

Active voice: *We have been constructing this house for two years;*

Passive voice: *The house has been under construction for two years.*

These sentences illustrate two different voice forms, with the passive voice formed using prepositional phrases. Here, the noun form of the verb *constructing* (i.e., *construction*) is used. Naturally, the syntactic roles of the object and the agent (we, house) in the sentence are also exchanged. This is a fundamental condition for constructing the passive voice. The sentences' Uzbek translations are as follows:

Active voice: *Biz bu uyni ikki yildan buyon quryapmiz;*

Passive voice: *Bu uy ikki yildan beri qurilyapti.*

The translations are formed in both active and passive voices, as the syntactic positions of the object and subject in Uzbek sentences also change, mirroring the structure of the original text. In the first sentence (in the active voice), the phrase acting as the complement becomes the subject in the passive sentence (*house*). However, in both sentences, the word belonging to the verb category is not transferred to another category. In English, it is possible for a verb to function as a noun. However, in Uzbek, a verbal noun, which is a form designated for verb functions, is still considered part of the verb category. Generally, the creation of the passive voice with prepositional constructions and the changes observed in its translation into Uzbek are reflected not in the essence of the voice category but in sentence construction.

The category of voice is also present in meanings expressed through non-finite forms of verbs. It is worth noting that there are several issues in converting active infinitives and active gerunds to their passive forms, and these issues are also reflected in translation. The use of the passive voice in each non-finite verb and analyses related to their translation are important for revealing the essence of the voice category. When the infinitive is used in the active voice, both the main action in the sentence and the action expressed by the infinitive are performed by the subject. It is known that, in English, sentences involving non-finite verbs also require a primary verb that expresses the subject, and such a verb is used in the sentence[4]. In the following sentence, the infinitive is used in the active voice, so we can see that both the main verb and the action expressed by the infinitive are performed by the subject (the word acting as the subject):

I am having a party next week and I want to invite all my friends to the party.

This sentence is translated into Uzbek as follows:

Kelgusi hafta ziyofat beryapman va unga hamma do'stlarimni taklif qilishni istayman.

In translation, the infinitive ("to invite") is rendered as a verbal noun in Uzbek ("taklif qilishni"). In Uzbek, the verbal noun is a non-conjugating form of the verb that does not change for person or number. "The formation, word structure, and its components, as well as the nature of each part, are essential in illustrating linguistic phenomena linked to morphological systems and their development." The verbal noun is also singled out as a form that serves noun-like functions of the verb. This is explained by its inability to perform some functions typical of verbs. However, as the verbal noun contains features typical of nouns, it can take possessive forms to indicate the subject. Additionally, its inability to directly express the subject and not acting as the predicate in a sentence illustrates the adequacy of the translation[5]. In English text, the performer of the action (first person singular – "I") appears twice. In Uzbek, the predicate often makes the subject clear, reducing the necessity for its explicit use. In this case, the performer of the action (first person singular, i.e., the speaker) is identified by the main verb functioning as the predicate ("istayman" – I want). In the passive infinitive, the main action is performed by the subject, while the action expressed by the infinitive is applied to the subject. In the following sentence, the passive infinitive is used:

I want to be invited to the party.

In this sentence, the action expressed by the main verb ("want") belongs to the performer functioning as the subject. However, the action expressed by the infinitive ("to be invited") indicates an action expected to be applied to the subject. This sentence is translated into Uzbek as follows:

Meni ziyofatga chaqirishlarini xohlayman.

In Uzbek translation, as in the original, the infinitive is expressed through a non-conjugating verb form (a verbal noun). However, it cannot be said that the subject is not expressed, as the possessive form added to the verbal noun shows that the performer of the action is in the third-person plural. Nevertheless, the performer of the action remains vague overall. This indicates that the verb in the active voice conveys the passive meaning. In other words, even if the passive infinitive is translated into Uzbek in the active voice, it still conveys the passive meaning. It is also possible to translate it directly in the passive form: *Men ziyofatga taklif qilinishni xohlayman (I want to be invited to the party)*. However, this would lead to some inconsistency in the sentence structure and logic.

In the use of active gerunds and passive gerunds, there are similarities with the use of active and passive infinitives. In sentences with an active gerund, the performer of both the main action and the action expressed by the gerund is considered the subject. In the following sentence, the active gerund is used:

I remember taking my pupil to the zoo last week.

In this sentence, the actions expressed by the main verb ("remember") and the gerund ("taking") were performed by the subject ("I"). This sentence is translated into Uzbek as follows:

O'tgan hafta o'quvchimni hayvonot bog'iga olib borganimni esladim.

In Uzbek translation, the performer of both actions is considered to be represented by the pronoun "I" in the subject position. The gerund ("taking") is translated as a verbal noun. In a sentence with a passive gerund, the action expressed by the main verb is performed by the subject, while the action expressed by the gerund is applied to the subject. In the following sentence, the passive gerund is used:

I remember being taken to the zoo by my teacher.

The Uzbek translation of this sentence is as follows:

O'qituvchim meni hayvonot bog'iga olib borganini eslayman.

It should be noted that the passive gerund has been translated into Uzbek in the active voice. Here, the main action is performed by the subject, while the action expressed by the gerund, translated as a participle, is performed by another person.

When translating English verb voices into Uzbek, some transformations accompany an adequate translation. This is due to the lack of full congruence between the voice categories in the two languages, differences in sentence construction, and the specific characteristics of the text being translated. The level of congruence in the translation of voice categories existing in both languages was found to be above fifty percent based on the analyzed sentences.

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